

Secondary ingestion of microplastics from zooplankton by larval fish a major route of exposure

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Abstract

The release of plastics into aquatic ecosystems and their effects within food webs is a growing concern. Plastic ingestion in animals such as bivalves, fish, birds, and mammals are established areas of study, but the effects of plastics on smaller animals, such as zooplankton and larval fish, are not as readily observed. Additionally, primary ingestion of plastic directly from the water is only one route of accumulation of plastic. We examined secondary ingestion of microplastics from zooplankton to larval fish in a model laboratory system. Rotifer (*Branchionus plicatilis*) readily accumulated 6 µm plastic microspheres in a concentration and time dependent manner. Larval zebrafish (*Danio rerio*) also ingested free plastic from the water, but the greatest uptake of plastic was seen to be ingested through secondary ingestion of plastic-fed rotifer. These experiments present a model experimental system in which to study secondary ingestion and movement of microplastics between feed and prey.

Keywords: marine plastic, zooplankton, secondary ingestion, rotifer, zebrafish, larval fish

1. Introduction

The abundance of plastic contamination in aquatic environments and their subsequent ingestion by birds, adult fish, and marine mammals is readily apparent. Microplastics, defined as plastics less than 5 mm in diameter, are of particular concern for ingestion because their size makes them bioavailable to a range of species and feeding behaviours (Wright et al., 2013). Microplastics may be produced intentionally, as in the case of plastics used as abrasives or as the result of the degradation of larger plastics through physical weathering or ingestion by biota (Dawson et al., 2018; Fendall and Sewell, 2009; Jahnke et al., 2017). Plastic ingestion in animals such as bivalves, fish, birds, and mammals are established areas of study. A smaller number of studies show that zooplankton (Cole et al., 2013; Lin, 2016; Rodrigues et al., n.d.; Savoca et al., 2020; Setälä et al., 2014) and larval fish (Huuskonen et al., 2020; Steer et al., 2017) in low trophic positions in the food web ingest microplastics directly from the water and that these plastics can accumulate in the gastrointestinal tracts or other locations in the body of the animal. Given the apparent phenomenon of plastic ingestion by animals at all trophic levels, it is reasonable to hy-

pothesize that plastic is being biomagnified up the food chain. A metanalysis of studies that examined trophic transfer of microplastics however, concluded that “MP biomagnification across a general marine food web is not supported [though nor is it invalidated] by current field observations, while results from the few laboratory studies supporting trophic transfer are hampered by using unrealistic exposure conditions” (Miller et al., 2020). To examine possible trophic transfer at low levels of food webs, this laboratory study investigates trophic transfer of microplastics between plankton and larval fish using concentrations of plastics found in polluted environments (Table 2).

Zebrafish (*Danio rerio*) are an increasingly popular organism used to study the effects of microplastic contamination on aquatic animals due to a variety of behavioral, life cycle, and genetic characteristics (Bhagat et al., 2020; Dai et al., 2014). Studies of larval zebrafish have shown a variety of toxicological effects, although typically at high concentrations of microplastics over long exposure periods (Bhagat et al., n.d.). Modification of toxicological properties of plastic delivered via secondary ingestion has been studied much less, without clear trends in the emerging research (Miller et al., 2020).

In this laboratory study, we examine the ingestion of microplastics in rotifer plankton and larval zebrafish independently as well as the transfer of microplastic to larval zebrafish by secondary ingestion of plastic-fed rotifer. We use a range of concentrations of microplastics found in polluted environments. Ingestion of concentrations of microplastics for different durations were observed and a model system for the further study of microplastic ingestion between zooplankton and larval fish developed. With this work, we demonstrate the importance of secondary ingestion as a likely key route for plastic ingestion in low-level aquatic food webs.

2. Methods

Rotifer culture

We obtained rotifer (*Branchionus plicatilis*) from active cultures maintained as live feed for aquaculture research at the Joe Brown Aquatic Research Facility (JBARB, Memorial University of Newfoundland). *B. plicatilis* is a commercially important rotifer species commonly used in the aquaculture industry for feeding larval fish. Approximately 1 million cleaned rotifers were transferred into filtered seawater (FSW) in a 20L bucket maintained at 26.5°C with an aquarium heater. An air stone inserted into a pipe with perforations running the depth of the bucket mixed and aerated the water.

We counted rotifer daily by adding 5 drops of vinegar to 10 ml of pre-mixed rotifer culture and counting 5 x 100 µl subsamples under a stereomicroscope (Nikon model SMZ745Y). Rotifer were fed an algal powder (Ori-One, Skretting) following the manufacturer’s instructions (i.e., 0.25 - 0.55 gm / million rotifer / day) in a 2 L emulsion fed to the tank at 6-hour intervals throughout the day with a peristaltic dosing pump.

Rotifer being prepared for use with the zebrafish, a freshwater species, was gradually reduced from a salinity of 29-31 ppt to 7-5 ppt over 10 days. Rotifer are capable of surviving in freshwater. We did not observe any changes in motility or speed of rotifer under these conditions although a more abrupt reduction in salinity would cause shock and a reduction in movement.

Although we tried using filter floss tied around the aeration tube as a means of cleaning the water, we found it to be better for culture yield to simply replace the water every 3 days by passage through a 500 μm filter to remove debris and then a 20 μm filter to collect rotifer which was washed into a clean bucket with new FSW. Rotifer for experiments was collected in a similar manner.

Rotifer exposure

We optimized the methods of feeding commercially created microplastic spheres to rotifer to observe ingestion behaviour of the zooplankton themselves and as a means of preparing plastic-fed rotifer to demonstrate secondary ingestion to larval fish. The plastics used in this experiment were 6 μm , yellow/green (YG) or red fluorescent polystyrene spheres (Polysciences, Warrington, PA), which are within the known size range of prey consumed by rotifer (Agasild and Nøges, 2005; Jeong et al., 2016). A working suspension of 500 $\mu\text{g}/\text{ml}$ was prepared in filtered seawater (FSW).

Up to 1 L of rotifer culture was collected from the active culture along with filtered water of the same salinity and temperature. Rotifer were filtered through a 70 μm mesh filter and then rinsed into a beaker with the FSW to a volume of 100 ml. Some dead or sessile rotifer would aggregate and float at the top of the water so a 70 μm cell strainer was used to skim them off and discard them. Counts were performed as described above and then the working culture of rotifer was diluted with FSW to 100 rotifer / ml and any floating clumps of rotifer again skimmed from the surface. 6 ml of this rotifer culture was transferred into individual wells of 6-well culture plates containing clean cell strainers before addition of plastic.

Exposure was done at 4 concentrations of plastic (0.04, 0.2, 1 and 5 $\mu\text{g}/\text{ml}$) at 6 durations of exposure (0.5, 2.5, 13, 63, 313 and 1560 min). Working stock plastic concentrations were confirmed with a hemocytometer (5.25 particles / ml at 1 $\mu\text{g}/\text{ml}$, i.e., 26,250 particles / L at the highest exposure concentration and 210 particles / L at the lowest). These are within the range of high concentrations of microplastics of a similar size found in the environment (Table 2). At each time point the appropriate cell strainers were removed and dipped into their own bath of neutral buffered formalin (NBF) to kill and preserve the rotifer and the plate with the remaining rotifer gently agitated. The cell-strainers were thoroughly rinsed with FSW to remove any free plastic. The strainers were inverted over clean beakers and rinsed with 2 ml of NBF to remove the bound rotifer which were stored at 4°C until analysis.

Egestion or clearing of microplastics from rotifer was examined in a separate experiment by feeding the rotifer plastics as above at 0.5 $\mu\text{g}/\text{ml}$ (2,625 particles/L) for 1 h and then transferring the rotifer to a plastic-free media. Rotifer were fed plastic within a cell strainer placed within the cell culture plate wells, thus allowing removal of the rotifer and for plastic to be washed off by repeated rinsing with filtered culture water. Rotifer were then collected as above at 10, 20 and 60 min after being allowed to depurate. During each time point, the remaining time point filters were transferred to plates with clean media.

Zebrafish culture

Fertilized zebrafish embryos were collected one day post fertilization from wildtype (strain AB) breeding adults (Kimmel et al., 1995; Umali et al., 2019). Animal experiments were approved by

Memorial University's Animal Care Committee in accordance with the standards of the Canadian Council on Animal Care (animal care approval was not required for the rotifer). Fish were divided into 6-well culture plates, 10 to a well, containing egg media (Ruzicka et al., 2019) with 30 mg/L 1-phenyl-2-thiourea (PTU). PTU acts to maintain clarity in the larval fish, which is required to later visualize the plastic inside of the fish. Zebrafish were maintained in an incubator with diurnal lighting at 28.5°C. Dead embryos, hatched larvae, and chorion were removed daily as well as a replacement of 1/3 of the media. At five days post fertilization we began adding rotifer to the larval culture. Rotifer were collected and concentrated as above and added to a concentration of 6000 rotifers / ml in the egg media culture plates. Debris and any non-viable fish or embryos were removed, and the media partially replaced every day.

Zebrafish exposure

We conducted two different exposure experiments. The first was designed to show the potential for larval zebrafish to ingest plastic from the water as well as through secondary ingestion. At 11 days post fertilization, fish were redistributed between wells so that each well contained 10 fish in 9 ml of egg media without PTU. Plates were set up to test five exposure time points in triplicate (23, 45, 90, 180 and 360 min). Plastic-fed rotifer (PFR) were prepared specifically for this portion of the experiment. 1 L of rotifer were collected from 5 ppt salinity rotifer culture, filtered through a 70 µm screen and resuspended in 100 ml of clean rotifer water as in the rotifer exposures. Following a count, this was diluted to 100 rotifer / ml. YG plastic was added to a final concentration of 0.5 µg/ml (2,625 microspheres / L) and the rotifer culture exposed to plastic as above for 60 min. These plastic-fed rotifers were filtered through a 70 µm mesh and thoroughly rinsed with egg water to remove any free plastic and resuspended in egg water to a concentration of 1000 rotifer / ml. Rotifer were examined to confirm ingestion of plastic (92% with plastic) and confirm motility and viability.

Three test conditions were used to observe secondary ingestion. In the first, free yellow/green (YG) plastic was added to the zebrafish wells at 0.5 µg/ml (2,625 microspheres / L), the same concentrations as used to feed the rotifer. No rotifers were added to this treatment. In the second, 1 ml plastic-fed rotifer was added to the zebrafish culture without any free plastic to a final concentration of 10 rotifer / ml. In the third, the conditions of free plastic and plastic-fed rotifer were combined. At the end of each time point, 1ml of 250 mg/L MS-222 anesthetic was added to each well in that set to kill the fish. The fish were removed by transfer pipette to NBF and stored at 4°C until analysis.

In a second experiment, different colours of plastic were used to observe exogenous vs. rotifer associated plastic. Red (R) 6 µm microspheres were used for this purpose in addition to yellow/green (YG). No difference in ingestion by rotifer was observed in trial experiments with an equal mix of red and yellow/green plastic. To each triplicate in sequence, first R plastic was added freely to water at a concentration of 0.5 µg/ml (2,625 microspheres / L) and then 1ml of plastic-fed rotifer that had ingested YG microspheres were added. A shorter time sequences was used to better understand the rapidity of plastic ingestion from the two different sources (23, 45, 90, 180, and 360 minutes).

Microscopy and analysis

Rotifer and zebrafish were imaged on a Nikon Ti-S inverted, epi-fluorescent microscope for yellow/green (YG, excitation 441 nm, emission 485 nm) or red (R, excitation 491/512 nm, emission

565 nm) microspheres, respectively. Rotifer were deposited on a petri dish and counts were made of all rotifer from each time point and plastic concentration. Zebrafish larvae were first individually deposited into wells of a 96 well, glass bottom, black microtiter plate. Individual counts of microspheres were made where possible, or where too much plastic was clumped together to allow for individual sphere counts recorded as >30. A small amount of crosstalk from the YG illumination would excite the R spheres, but this was eliminated by using a ND filter which had no impact on the ease of detection of the YG spheres.

We performed counts by eye for rotifer and zebrafish. Additionally, we used digital imaging to quantify plastic fluorescence in the zebrafish. Using ImageJ Ver. 1.53c (Schneider et al., 2012), background was subtracted, and the fluorescent channel used to measure total fluorescence and generate plot profiles of intensity from the head to anus. Comparison of intensity data to manual count data did not indicate a significant difference in results, so manual count data has been used throughout.

Statistical analysis

We used R 3.6.2 (R Core Team, 2020) to analyze the statistical significance of the number of plastic microspheres ingested at different concentrations and time scales. Comparisons of bead counts between time points was done with t-tests or One-way Analysis of Variance (ANOVA) with Tukey pairwise comparisons post hoc to explore pairwise comparisons. A simple linear regression was used to compare visual to digital counts of microspheres. Values are considered significant when $p < 0.05$ although all values are reported.

3. Results

Rotifer ingestion / egestion

Rotifer were fed 6 μm diameter microspheres at four concentrations of plastics for five durations from 0.5 to 1560 min. Rotifer that were actively feeding, as indicated by movement, and beating of cilia of the corona, immediately consumed the microspheres that entered the area of fluid flow from the corona. The water currents created by the corona readily drew microspheres into the mouth and no rejection of plastic was visually observed. In tests where both the YG and R plastic were mixed, no preference was observed for either plastic ($t(26) = 0.60, p = 0.55$). Capture and recovery of rotifer from the filter screen was variable, as shown by the count values in Table 1. Not all rotifer ingested plastic; the percentage of rotifer which had ingested at least one plastic microsphere ranged from 0% for the lowest concentration at 2.5 $\mu\text{g}/\text{mL}$ and 13 min, to a high of 84% for the highest concentration of 5 $\mu\text{g}/\text{mL}$ at 63 min. For all time points, plastic counts increased with concentration and for all concentrations, ingestion counts of individual microspheres and the number of animals that ingested plastics within the test population increased with time (Table 1; Figure 1).

Table 1: Rotifer that ingested plastic (+) and total numbers of rotifer (N) collected, presented as percentage (%) of rotifer with at least one microsphere (ms) consumed.

$\mu\text{g/ml}$	ms/L	0.5 min		2.5 min		13 min		63 min		1560 min	
		(+ / N)	(%)	(+ / N)	(%)						
0.04	210	1/269	0.4	0/6	0.0	0/39	0.0	15/229	6.6	6/55	10.9
0.2	1050	2/154	1.3	15/193	7.8	14/135	10.4	37/180	20.6	47/178	26.4
1	5250	5/190	2.6	27/180	15.0	92/161	57.1	90/167	53.9	58/169	34.3
5	26250	10/64	15.6	50/156	32.1	50/65	76.9	85/101	84.2	96/152	63.2

Fig. 1. Number of polystyrene microspheres ingested by rotifer over time and at different concentrations. Average number of microspheres per rotifer with standard error. Inset shows overlay of brightfield and fluorescent images of rotifer with ingested microspheres (fluorescing in green).

Time (min)	Egestion	
	(+ / N)	(%)
0	91/107	85.0%
10	30/40	75.0%
20	30/41	73.2%
60	30/42	71.4%

Table 2: Rotifer that ingested plastic (+) and total numbers of rotifer (N) collected, presented as percentage (%) of rotifer with at least one microsphere consumed.

Figure 2: Egestion of plastic microspheres from rotifer over time. Average number of microspheres per rotifer with standard error.

Rotifer did not appear to clear microplastic rapidly, and egestion rates do not have a steadily temporal trend like ingestion rates (Figure 2). Although there was an initial decrease in mean plastic counts at 10 min, only the 20 min time point was significantly different from the baseline value (ANOVA, $p = 0.007$).

Zebrafish ingestion

Zebrafish larvae ingested plastic directly from the water or via feeding on rotifer. Zebrafish larvae which were fed the plastic-fed rotifer contained the greatest amount of plastic. On average, larval fish contained 50 (SE = 8.12) microspheres after 5 hours of feeding. Like with the rotifer, feeding was bimodal with some fish not feeding at all (see Table 3). In each of the three time points, the mean numbers of microspheres ingested was higher for the zebrafish fed plastic-fed rotifer than in the fish in water containing free plastic only, however this difference was significant only for 3 hours ($p = 0.015$) and 5 hours ($p = 0.008$) post-feeding and not 7 hours ($p = 0.078$, Figure 3). Zebrafish that were mixed with unfed rotifer and free plastic (P+R) had an overall intermediate level of ingested plastic which was indistinguishable from P or PFR groups for each time point.

We conducted a second experiment to further assess differences in secondary ingestion of plastic versus directly from the surrounding water when these conditions occurred simultaneously, using microspheres of two different fluorescence colours. Red plastic was added as an exogenous source and yellow/green as the source fed to rotifer which would only be available by secondary ingestion. Additional time points were added compared to the prior experiment (23, 45, 90, 180 and 360 min) with an exposure done 12 days post fertilization, otherwise methods were as above. At 23 min, larvae contained a mean of 4.23 (SE = 1.47) microspheres, which rapidly increased at 45 min and above where counts in fish which ingested plastic were too high to enumerate in most cases. No fish ingested red plastic, indicating secondary ingestion was the only route of plastics ingestion in this experiment.

Counts by digital means vs. eye produced similar results with a linear relationship between these observations ($p < 0.001$, $R^2 = 0.61$). Data shown uses the technician count although the digital methods allowed for an examination of transit within the digestive system of the fish. Plastic was principally seen in the anterior intestinal lumen and there was no clear progress from anterior to posterior in the time span examined. Microplastic was distributed linearly within this space, with some clumping likely due to association with rotifer (Figure 5).

Figure 3: Ingestion of plastic in zebrafish from suspended plastic (P), secondary ingestion of plastic fed rotifer (PFR) and a mix of rotifer (unfed) and free plastic added to the water (P+R). P and P+R free plastics concentration was $0.5 \mu\text{g/ml}$ (2,625 microspheres / L). Error bars show standard error.

Figure 5: Transit plot. Position is normalized to equal mouth (0) to anus (1) and total fluorescence at each point converted to a frequency value represented by the points and boxplots.

Table 3: Zebrafish with ingested plastic (+) and total numbers of zebrafish larvae (N) collected, presented as percentage (%) of larvae with at least one microsphere consumed. P = plastic free in the water, PFR = plastic fed rotifer and P+R = a mix of plastic and rotifer added at the same time to the larval culture.

Time (h)	P		P+R		PFR	
	(+ / N)	(%)	(+ / N)	(%)	(+ / N)	(%)
3	14/17	82.4%	12/13	92.3%	15/17	88.2%
5	18/21	85.7%	14/16	87.5%	20/20	100.0%
7	15/16	93.8%	11/13	84.6%	17/17	100.0%

4. Discussion

In these experiments we examined the ingestion of microplastics by a particular zooplankton (rotifer) and a larval fish (zebrafish), focusing on trophic transfer from the former to the later. It remains difficult to examine plastic ingestion at this scale *in situ*, so laboratory models provide a means to examine hypotheses about routes of plastic ingestion for these types of organisms.

Microplastics in zooplankton

Microplastic was ingested by rotifer from the water. Other laboratory experiments on rotifer have made similar observations (Jeong et al., 2016) over a period of days, whereas we observed rapid ingestion over shorter periods, starting with 30 seconds and accelerating after an hour. Rotifer ingested plastic in a bimodal way, i.e., many rotifer ingested no plastic at all. Frequency of occurrence (FO%) of plastic ingestion within the population ranged from 0.4% at the shortest time (0.5 min) and concentration (0.04 $\mu\text{m}/\text{ml}$ or 21 microspheres/L) to 84.2% at 63 minutes at the highest concentration (5 $\mu\text{m}/\text{ml}$ or 2,625 microspheres / L). At just over a day (1560 minutes), the longest period, between 10.9% and 63.2% of the population had ingested microspheres at the lowest and highest concentrations, respectively. Higher concentrations also resulted in higher average counts of microspheres ingested by individual rotifer. Thus, concentration and time are determining factors in ingestion rates, both within the population and in terms of the number of microspheres ingested. Differences in the efficiency of feeding may be due to several factors, including changes between sessile to motile behavior, morbidity, or mortality during the experiment. The amount of plastic found in rotifers increased in a time and concentration dependent manner. It was not likely impacted by egestion, which was slower and was not impacted by time or concentration. We found no other studies of rotifer plastic egestion for comparison.

The species of plankton is also a consideration. We used *Branchionus plicatilis*, but Setälä et al. (2014) exposed the rotifer *Synchaeta spp.* to nearly identical conditions (2000 microspheres / ml) as our own high concentration condition with similar sized (10 μm) polystyrene microspheres and found that after 12 hours, 18% had ingested plastics compared to 63% at our closest time scale (25 hours). While some species are known to differentiate between plastics and food (Kim et al., 2019), we did not observe any intentional avoidance or “spitting up” of plastics.

Larval fish and secondary ingestion

Our observations support the hypothesis that a greater amount of plastic ingestion will occur via secondary ingestion rather than directly from the water, and that ingestion directly from water will change whether there are prey present or not. Measured independently, zebrafish larvae,

which only obtained plastic from secondary ingestion, had, on average, more than double the amount of plastic over three time points than the fish within the plastic suspension in water, regardless of concentration. Yet, after exposure with one colour of plastic free in the water and the other within rotifer showed only ingestion by the secondary route and none by primary ingestion (Table 3). The difference between larvae fish ingesting plastics when they were free in the water, but not ingesting free plastics when rotifer were available may indicate selective feeding in conditions with different availability of prey items. Free-plastic ingestion may also be explained by gulping and pouncing behaviour in which larval fish appeared to be striking at and gulping non-existent prey. While Kim et al. (2019) found that adult zebrafish recognized microplastics and avoided ingesting them, their study used comparatively large plastics (247.5 μm) compared to our 6 μm size scaled to be ingestible by prey as well as predator. Kim et al. (2019) did not explicitly test for secondary ingestion, but they did find that adult zebrafish had a lower accumulation percentage when only free microplastics were present. This aligns with our findings.

Experimental model

This work developed a relatively simple experimental model for examining secondary ingestion from zooplankton to larval fish. Rotifer plankton (*Branchionus plicatilis*) are typically found in saltwater or brackish conditions and are a euryhaline species found globally, and a primary food source for aquaculture species (Suatoni et al., 2006). Zebrafish (*Danio rerio*) is a freshwater species native to central and south Asia (Engeszer et al., 2007). Both are readily available experimental animals with well-established rearing and experimental protocols, which is why they were chosen for this work. Zebrafish are a key emerging model to study micro- and nano- plastic toxicity (Bhagat et al. 2020). This means the system could be reproduced readily by many labs to improve understanding of secondary ingestion, even if these organisms are not likely to encounter one another in natural environments. Because of the fluorescence of the plastic used and the translucence of the rotifer, microspheres could be easily observed within the transparent rotifer and zebrafish larvae. Visual counts in zebrafish were comparable to digital quantification, so the method should work well with non-fluorescent plastics, removing the need for epi-fluorescent microscopes.

Adapting the method to other species would chiefly be dependent on a good understanding of the culture and behaviour of that species, especially larval fish, for which zebrafish proved the easiest to use. Initial attempts to use locally relevant fish species (Atlantic cod [*Gadus morhua*] and Cunner [*Tautoglabrus adspersus*]), for example, failed due to poor breeding results. Unlike those species, zebrafish breeding is not seasonally dependent, allowing for easily repeated experiments. We were able to acclimate the rotifer to a lower saltwater concentration while maintaining their motility and feeding behaviour. Rotifer have been used in experimental systems as feed for zebrafish¹⁷ and they stimulate normal predation behavior even though the combination is ecologically unnatural. An exposure time of 11-12 days post-fertilization (DPF) was chosen to introduce plastic early in the maturation of the fish. In this period the fish are transitioning from obtaining nutrition from the yolk-sac to hunting.

Overall, this experiment speaks to the importance of considering secondary ingestion in microplastic experiments with animals that serve as a Trojan Horse, bypassing rejection methods of the predator animal. The exact developmental timing and triggering of hunting and other ingestion behaviour may be labile (Rønnestad et al., 2013). This is something that can be elucidated by repeating experiments at different ages, at different times of day, with or without food, under

different lighting regimes and different salinities or other water quality parameters. Likewise, the effect of different colours, sizes and shapes on uptake by larval fish can be examined, as they have been shown to impact ingestion, accumulation, and egestion in other laboratory studies (Gray and Weingsten, 2017; Graham et al., 2019; Windsor et al., 2019; Xu et al., 2019).

When considering these results for implications for other species, it is important to note that in freshwater fish, “drinking” is an osmotic balance that can be maintained by the gills and the skin, so little water is directed into the digestive tract as in saltwater fish. Consequently, the amount of free plastic ingested by saltwater fish may be higher than we observed with freshwater zebrafish.

Environmental relevance

In the last five years, a critique of laboratory studies that investigate plastic ingestion has emerged in relation to the environmental relevance of study designs (Phuong et al., 2016; Mouneyrac et al., 2017; Carbery et al., 2018). Core among these critiques is how “most laboratory experiments have been performed with MP concentrations of a higher order of magnitude than those found in the field. Consequently, the ingestion and associated effects observed in exposed organisms have corresponded to great contaminant stress, which does not mimic the natural environment” (Phuong et al., 2016: 111). In her review of the impacts of microplastics on plankton, Lin (2016) advised that, “Future research on the impact of microplastics on plankton needs to further improve balancing realistic environmental conditions with the practical challenges of experimental methodology and laboratory setup to produce meaningful information.” Heeding these calls, we aimed to use concentrations that would work in laboratory conditions while also reflecting highly polluted environments is an effort to strike this balance.

Finding environmentally relevant concentrations for this study was challenging, as the vast majority of microplastic surveys in surface and suspended water use mesh sizes much larger than the 6 µm plastic used here, often 300–333 µm (e.g. see reviews by; Li et al 2018). This is a feasible cut off size for surface water studies, but the result of this is that the state of the knowledge on microplastics in water are for plastics 300 µm and larger, the concentration of smaller microplastics is either unknown or underestimated (Ripken et al., 2021; Rønnestad et al., 2019). To make direct comparisons of concentrations between most field studies and laboratory studies is thus difficult. Plastic concentrations are not always reported in consistent units (Li 2018; Yu et al., 2020). To enable comparison between this study and others, we have consistently provided two common types of reporting in laboratory (µg/ml) and field studies (particles/L).

Table 2: Concentrations of microspheres used in this experiment compared to environmentally relevant concentrations found in field studies. Selections based on studies with similar size ranges to those used in this study (6 µm). Entries marked with an asterisk (*) were calculated from study data to obtain particles/L for the specific size listed.

This study			Field studies			
µg/ml	particles/L	Experiment	Environment	particles/L	Plastic size (µm)	Citation
0.04	210	Rotifer exposure	Surface water, Nakagusku, island of Okinawa	275	1-20	Ripken et al., 2020*
0.2	1,050	Rotifer exposure	Treated wastewater	338-628	1-10	Pivokonsky et al., 2018
0.5	2,625	Rotifer egestion, Plastic-fed rotifer, zebrafish	Raw water (sewage treatment)	1,473 - 3,605	1-10	Pivokonsky et al., 2018
1	5,250	Rotifer exposure	Nearshore North Pacific sub-surface water	8,277 (avg)	5-333	Brandon et al., 2020
5	26,250	Rotifer exposure	n/a	n/a	n/a	n/a

The concentrations used in the rotifer experiments ranged from 210 to 26,250 microspheres / L, and in the zebrafish experiments were 2,625 microspheres / L. Most of our exposure concentrations are estimated to be within what has been reported for a range of environmental concentrations, except for our highest concentration for the rotifer exposure (Table 2). A literature search for field studies that targeted plastics in smaller size ranges under 300 µm found that many of our concentrations were characteristic of highly polluted marine and wastewaters. Results show that concentrations of plastics in the lowest concentration ranges produced useful information on primary and secondary ingestion, as well as egestion. It is likely that for some laboratory studies on microplastics, lower environmentally relevant concentrations can be used to gather data. At the very least, studies can include environmentally relevant concentrations in a wider range of concentrations studied.

This study used commercially produced microspheres. Other studies have shown that shape, size, and erosion can affect accumulation and toxicity of microplastic ingestion (Gray et al., 2017; Qiao et al 2019; Ogonowski et al., 2016). Lehtiniemi et al. (2018) found that size, more than shape, influences plastics ingested by small predators, though the plastics they were investigating were larger than the ones in this study (200-500 µm). In natural settings, microplastics are found in a mix of morphologies (especially fibers) and sizes, and consideration should be given to how these factors would affect ingestion percentage and count. We do not know if size, shape, and morphology would also affect secondary ingestion differently than primary ingestion.

Although this model examines plastic ingestion from rotifer to larval fish in a controlled environment with two species, the results suggest that secondary ingestion of plastic in aquatic environments is the greater route of plastic loading into the body of some aquatic animals in comparison to direct ingestion from the water. This should be examined in more natural contexts, although methods to identify small plastics in this size range are currently limited and difficult to apply widely²². One study that examined microplastic ingestion of plankton in situ, noted high rates of plastic ingestion in plankton when environmental plastic concentrations were similar to our rotifer exposure at 1 µg/ml (5,250 particles/L) in the North Pacific (Brandon et al., 2020). They used epifluorescence microscopy and found that 100% of salps collected had ingested microplastics,

with concentrations varying due to geographic and life history factors. If, as our study suggests, larval fish ingest more plastic through their consumption of plankton than through primary ingestion, and plankton are known to ingest plastic, then it is important to examine the geographic and species-specific traits that render certain food webs more susceptible to plastic pollution.

5. Conclusion

This study found that secondary ingestion, rather than ingestion of plastics free in the water, was the main source of plastic ingestion by larval fish. At the same time, if no prey is available, larval fish will ingest some free plastics, likely through pouncing and gulping behaviours designed to capture prey. However, these ingestion rates were consistently lower than through secondary ingestion. We further found that concentration and time impact the frequency of plastic ingestion (FO%) within the population as well as the number of plastics consumed by individuals.

This study focused on plankton and larvae fish with microplastics that were relevant to this portion of the food web (6 μm). Impacts of plastics to the health of key microfauna prey species and early developmental macrofauna life stages are often invisible to standard methods, as they do not leave readily found mortalities within which to observe plastics or are too small for the tools used in many standard survey methods. The ultimate trajectory of this line of research would be to determine if the presence of microplastic in aquatic environments is so much as to reduce zooplankton abundance or bioavailability to the point where it has subsequent impacts on the food web given their key role in marine ecosystems. Globally, zooplankton abundance is in decline. Although the evidence suggests that global warming is driving this decline, the additional stress of microplastics has yet to be quantified, though there is important emerging research on the interaction of climate change and plastic ingestion (Iwalaye et al., 2021).

Our experiments did not directly set out to observe toxic effect of plastics to the study organisms, although this has been reported elsewhere. Jeong et al. (2016) reported that polystyrene microspheres of the type used here produced a variety of deleterious effects in *B. koreanus* including reductions in growth rate, fecundity and lifespan. Impacts on all life-stages of zebrafish have been more widely studied (Bhagat et al., 2020) although the impact of secondary ingestion on toxicity is still in its infancy (Miller et al., 2020). Regardless of potential cellular toxic effects, the accumulation of plastics in zooplankton and fish guts could affect animal nutrition insofar as plastic is taking the place of food. For instance, depleted energy reserves have been observed in marine worms, likely because of a combination of reduced feeding activity, longer gut residence time of plastics, and inflammation (Cole et al., 2015). Within the rotifer, plastic was often observed as a bolus of material that occupied much of the gut space (Figure 5), indicating that rotifer may become satiated by microplastics, potentially affecting food uptake and nutrition. Cole et al. (2015), found that the presence of polystyrene beads of 7.3 μm significantly reduced algal ingestion rates in the North Atlantic copepod species, *Centropages typicus*.

Understanding the role of secondary ingestion of microplastics in zooplankton and early life stage aquatic animals is an important and understudied component of understanding the fate and effects of microplastic in the aquatic environment. Our work begins to build tools to specifically examine the many aspects of this interaction.

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